

Facile Rearrangement of a Furoquinoline

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Rearrangement of the furoquinoline alkaloid balfurodine (1) on acetylation to the pyranoquinoline, isobalfurodine acetate (2) has been reported earlier^{1,2}. Ring expansion has also been observed when balfurodine is treated with methyl sulphate, isobalfurodine methosulphate being formed by rearrangement. Instances of similar rearrange-

ment are unknown in the relatively simple 2-alkyl-4-methylfuro[2,3-*b*]quinolines.

We have observed the facile rearrangement of 2,3-dihydro-2-ethyl-4-methylfuro[2,3-*b*]quinoline³ (3) to 3,4-dihydro-2,5-dimethyl-2*H*-pyrano[2,3-*b*]quinoline (4) on treatment with sulphuric acid (Scheme 1). Compound 3 (1 g) was heated

NOTES

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

with concentrated sulphuric acid (10 ml) under a CaCl_2 guard tube on a steam-bath for 30 min. The cooled mixture was poured into water (60 ml), filtered and the filtrate on basification with ammonia gave **4** (96%) which was recrystallised from ethanol (20%) as colourless needles (tlc pure), m.p. 146° (Found: C, 78.76; H, 7.12; N, 6.50. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}$ requires: C, 78.82; H, 7.09; N, 6.56%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 605, 1 560 and 1 490 cm^{-1} (pyranoquinoline absorptions³); δ (CDCl_3) 1.54 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 2- CH_3), 2.1 (2H, m, CH_2 -3), 2.53 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3), 2.9 (2H, m, CH_2 -4), 4.4 (1H, m, H-2) and 7.23–8.0 (4H, m, ArH); picrate, needles from ethanol, m.p. 225 – 26° . The product was found to be identical with an authentic specimen⁴ of **4** by m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra.

A possible mechanism involving the polar transition state, **5** and the hydroxyquinoline, **6** is

suggested for the rearrangement (Scheme 2). It was also observed that the closely related 2,3-dihydro-2,4-dimethylfuro[2,3-*b*]quinoline does not rearrange under similar conditions.

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References

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